

SCHOOL PUPILS INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS

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Abstract

This article describes the intellectual development of education in the importance illuminated , as well as, intellectual development of pedagogical mechanisms about so'z is doing.

Keywords: intelligence, intelligence, education, creativity, talent, creative potential, abilities, pedagogy, psychology.

The important role of education listed the intellectual development in readers'l plays. Intellectual and creative potential to increase the education process and the essence of this process is characteristic for certain which appeared in qonuniyat reflects internal communication and relationships.

Readers profit educational society in the process of intellectual development bearing, put the person which meets the requirements of the ethics xulqiy will ensure that qualifications and skills. To the mind of the student to achieve this, the outlook and systematic, regular effect.

The process of development of creative potential, none of them gets overlooked if it becomes difficult to achieve the ultimate goal. These psychological aspects of intellectual and creative abilities into account the form of readers olingandagina rivojlantrishga it is to create. Readers of the formation of intellectual and creative abilities of the following sources and its development 1- in the form of this expressioncan sh:

C,h,then the prime minister-1

Education-education focused on the importance of education to give them a certain goal in the process. The process of education to develop intellectual and creative abilities to be creative shakllantirmasdan readers will not stand them.

The essence of the educational process and intellectual function that develops readers aimed at any target planned and fulfilled by the caregivers of the series methods are defined:

1. Awakening of creative intellectual potential readers the form of character development and planning.
2. Create a method of carrying out the development of this character to go looking for the source of the intellectual or creative potential increases the service is found.
3. Theoretical and practical sources in which to work where and which serve for the purpose specified planning.

Thus the implementation of the plan into the works of the lord, that take readers are also in the process of the education system to develop the creative intellectual potential and intellectual and physical performance boosts of human society will go.

The development of the reader's intellectual capacity to put readers on the right path-the set of creative activity of students of the implementation of measures we will divide them into two groups:

"Intellectual" of the group

- 1) "Insight", "Talent", "Possible" intellectual games such as the transfer;
- 2) "The best chronicler, mathematician, dasturlovchi, physical, biological and philologist ... etc." to conduct in the name of the contest;
- 3) scientific direction of the organization of work in scientific conferences;
- 4) "Young programmers", "young astronomers", "young inventor", "curators Young", "Young technicians", "radiotexnik are Young", "young economist" is to establish the club as.

"A creative and talented students" group

- 1) "The best poem, picture, photo, embroidery, so'zana etc." to conduct in the name of the contest;
- 2) "Cheerful and resourceful" the conduct of the bout of the team of the club;
- 3) "The best nurse, accountant, cook, hand, suvchi, crop research, terimchi etc." to conduct in the name of the contest;
- 4) "Young, healthy", "young musician", "young readers", "young creative" as the drafting of the club;
- 5) creative creative at night and readers of the exhibition the organization;
- 6) developmpeople, holidays, national holiday on the occasion of international and apply a set of events to produce andgincrease.
- 7) the day he was born the night of the feast of our great thinkers dedicated to organized to see the events of the scene;

8) kompozitsiya dedicated to artistic independently any one subject of preparation;

9) amateur circles as revive his work and competitions will be held for the organization;

10) creative work of popularization of the complex;

11) the establishment of the prize of the best creative reader;

12) a competition under the organization of talented students of the year's best posts. Also the development of intellectual and creative potential readers, readers for the introduction of regular work activities in each lesson teachers should monitor each amaliyatga creative.

Below are students of the development of intellectual and creative potential use of the method for stir come about samples:

Mind charhi conduct of the exercise: this is a different rebus, krasovordlar withdrawals, the organization of chess and checkers games in the form of competitions to enter.

Transfer to the young fellow of the circle of writers: readers this creative skills, talent boosts aimed at the event consists of a set of go. For example, among students who work with students while sharing skills and journalistic writer.

Cha sports game and the conduct of agile aqqonlar: this includes the conduct of sports competitions of all kinds.

Mushoira, g'azalxonlik transfer of contest: this method will be entered through the creation g'azal poems and readers. Thus, the "She'ga night" event includes qtkazish.

Cheerful and resourceful conduct of the contest: this contest readers through art, theatre and cataloging ingenuity and skill will be increased the interest to be assessed.

The teacher-student work of improvement: the implementation of this method of the disciples who it works best for teachers who are very pleased and

grateful-is the popularization of the work of teachers.

Readers of all creative talent and the skill of the assessment of course work, it is desirable to reward them with a different gift and certificate of honor.

Despite the theoretical and practical abilities as listed above to the example of the problems of psychology and pedagogy and its development is considered one of the most difficult issues. Analyzer the power of intuition abilities, actions and asabi physical and mental processes which is related to the characteristics of the nervous system as muvofiqlashgan natural talent, talent, as well as develops under the influence of external social media.

Thus, the person of decisive importance in the process of formation of intellectual development towards the needs of the period in the period o'quvchilik the formation and development of spiritual qualities they can also be positive, find life purpose and the active life in the work of consolidation and explain the perspective of the decision it is necessary to use to the maximum extent.

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